

AWARENESS OF TERATOGENIC DRUGS AMONG NURSING INTERNS

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Abstract

Background: Teratogenicity caused by drugs can largely be prevented through increased awareness about the rational use of medications during pregnancy. The harmful effects of a drug on the developing fetus depend on the stage of embryological development at the time of exposure. Timely knowledge about teratogenic risks is crucial, especially in settings where many pregnant women receive care from non-specialist health professionals. This study aimed to assess the awareness of teratogenic drugs among nursing interns in Pakistan to identify knowledge gaps and inform educational improvements.

Methods: A descriptive cross sectional study was conducted among 200 nursing interns from three tertiary care hospitals in Islamabad. Data were collected using a structured questionnaire covering awareness of teratogens, appropriate counseling timing, and critical periods of fetal susceptibility. Statistical analysis was performed using SPSS, applying descriptive statistics and chi square tests to explore associations between demographic variables and awareness.

Results: Most participants (91.5%) were aware of the term teratogen, and 86.5% recognized that drugs can cause teratogenicity. Awareness of teratogenicity across all trimesters was 82.5%, and 74.5% knew about potential outcomes. Only 41% identified the pre-pregnancy period as the ideal time for counseling, while 45.5% recognized the first eight weeks as the most susceptible period. Significant associations were found between gender and awareness ($p = 0.014$) and between hospital affiliation and trimester-related knowledge ($p = 0.036$).

Conclusions: While overall awareness was good, specific gaps remain regarding counseling timing and critical fetal periods, highlighting the need to strengthen educational content on teratogenicity during nursing training.

INTRODUCTION

Teratogenicity refers to the ability of some medicinal agents to cause abnormal development of cells of the body hence leading to physiological, psychological or biochemical changes in fetus identifiable at birth or

subsequently at a later stage of life (Alhamdan, et al., 2020). The administration of thalidomide during the 20th century resulted in severe congenital limb malformation or phocomelia and substantial numbers

of fetal loss. (Vargesson, et al., 2015). This tragedy paved the way for shifting in the medication regulation and prenatal safety. Even with greater awareness throughout the world and improvements in laws like the food and drug administration (FDA's) Pregnancy and Lactation Labeling Rule (PLLR) many medical professionals and pregnant females still lack understanding of the risks linked with teratogenic medicines. (Tsamantioti & Hashmi, et al., 2024) Congenital defects have complex pathophysiology and manifestations that have genetic and environmental

basis. Environmental teratogens radiation, infections, and untreated chronic illnesses, are assumed to be responsible for 15% of all congenital malformations. Conditions include epilepsy, thyroid problems, gestational diabetes, and the medications used to treat them have been linked to known teratogenic issues. (Alhamdan, et al 2020). In low and middle income countries (LMICs) for South Asia (Southern Asia), the under-5 child mortality rate declined by ~72% from 1990 to 2022; number of under-5 deaths fell from ~5 million in 1990 to ~1.3 million in 2022 (UNICEF October 2023). In countries like Pakistan, where nursing staff and interns are one of the basic care providers of prenatal care, improving mother and child health outcomes depends on their knowledge and understanding of teratogenic medications. Study conducted in Saudi Arabia suggest that Healthcare professionals usually, lack confidence and expertise while giving drugs during pregnancy Alshammari et al., 2014, Nnamdi Azikiwe et al., 2024). As per our knowledge no study in Pakistan is conducted to assess the knowledge of nursing interns' about teratogenic risks. The purpose of this study is to highlight persisting educational gaps to promote safer pregnancies and healthier births. Understanding the impact of teratogenic drugs is crucial for the healthcare professionals, especially nursing interns who plays a vital role in patients care and education. Unfortunately, a lack of awareness about the harmful effects of certain medications and substances during pregnancy remains a widespread issue especially in low and middle income countries like Pakistan (PAFMJ 2023). This study addressed the existing gaps in knowledge about teratogenic drugs among nursing interns. Many birth defects and pregnancy

complications can be prevented if expecting mothers receive the right information at the right time. Nursing interns, who are often directly involved in patient care and counseling, must be well informed about these risks to effectively educate and protect their patients. By addressing the gaps it will highlight the areas where further education and training are needed. This study will hope to support improvements in nursing curricula, encourage better clinical practices, and contribute to overall maternal and child health.

METHODOLOGY

A descriptive cross sectional study was conducted among 200 nursing interns from three different tertiary care hospitals in Islamabad. Data were collected through a structured questionnaire which was previously used. It included basic awareness questions on teratogenic drugs, appropriate timing for counseling, and periods of fetal susceptibility. Frequency distributions were computed to describe awareness levels, and chi square tests were applied to assess associations between awareness variables and demographic factors such as age, gender, and hospital affiliation. Ethical approval was obtained from IRB of Rawal Institute of Health Sciences. Statistical analyses were performed using Chi square test, and the results were interpreted accordingly. Ethical approval for the study was obtained from the heads of both participating institutions. The questionnaire used for data collection is presented in Table 1 below.

RESULTS

The term "teratogen" was familiar to 91.5% of nursing interns. 86.5% of people were aware that drugs can result in birth abnormalities. Just 41% of respondents were aware that teratogenic concerns should be discussed with women prior to conception. The first eight weeks are the most vulnerable for fetal deformity, however less than half (45.5%) were aware of this. Gender differences in awareness were significant ($p = 0.014$). Knowledge of trimesters was similarly impacted by hospital affiliation ($p = 0.036$). 82.5% of respondents were aware of teratogenicity in all trimesters. There are gaps in knowledge about fetal fragility and when to seek counseling.

Table 1: Questionnaire.

Sr. no.	Questionnaire
1.	Are you aware of the term teratogen?
a.	Yes
b.	No
2.	Can drugs cause teratogenicity?
a.	Yes
b.	No
3.	Do you think that teratogenicity due to drugs can occur during all the three trimesters?
a.	Yes
b.	No
4.	Can you name US-FDA fetal risk categories of teratogenic drugs?
a.	Yes
b.	No
If yes, name it:	
5.	Can you name first drug teratogen?
a.	Yes
b.	No
If yes, name it and the associated anomaly it caused in fetus:	
6.	Can you name two teratogenic drugs?
a.	Yes
b.	No
If yes, names:	
7.	Are you aware of the results/outcomes of teratogenicity?
a.	Yes
b.	No
8.	Do you think that a history of teratogenic drug intake should be elicited from all pregnant females?
a.	Yes
b.	No
9.	Which time of pregnancy is most appropriate to counsel a lady about teratogens?
a.	1 st trimester
b.	2 nd trimester
c.	3 rd trimester
d.	Before pregnancy
10.	Which time of intrauterine life is most susceptible to teratogens
a.	First 8 weeks
b.	Last 4 weeks
c.	Throughout the pregnancy

Table 2: Responses towards awareness of teratogenicity.

Questions	Yes	No
Are you aware of the term teratogen?	183	17
Can drugs cause teratogenicity	173	27
Teratogenicity can occur during all trimesters?	165	35
Are you aware of the results/outcomes of teratogenicity?	149	51
History of teratogenic drug intake should be elicited?	151	49

Figure 1: Awareness regarding term teratogen.

Figure 2: Can drugs cause teratogenicity.

Figure 3: Most appropriate time of pregnancy for counselling regarding teratogenicity.

Figure 4: Most susceptible time of pregnancy for teratogenicity.

DISCUSSION

This study evaluated nursing interns' knowledge of teratogenic medicines in Islamabad and discovered that while general understanding was adequate, there are still significant gaps in some areas. The majority of participants were aware that some medications can result in prenatal abnormalities and had heard of teratogens. These results are positive and show that a solid foundation in drug safety during pregnancy is provided by nursing education (PAFMJ, 2023; Kareem et al., 2023). There was, however, little information available regarding the most crucial fetal times and the best times for counseling. The first eight weeks were properly identified as the most critical time for fetal development by less than half of the participants, and less than half acknowledged the importance of pre-pregnancy counseling. According to these results, students may not completely comprehend the practical consequences of teratogenicity in clinical settings, even when they are aware of the concept (Kareem et al., 2023; Einarson et al., 2023). Studies in other low- and middle-income nations have found similar outcomes, with medical personnel demonstrating rudimentary knowledge but lacking confidence when it came to advising expectant mothers about the safety of their medications (PAFMJ, 2023; Prenatal Care Initiation and Exposure to Teratogenic Medications, 2023). These knowledge gaps may be exacerbated by a lack of focus on preconception education and a lack of clinical exposure to pregnancy-related medications (WHO, 2024). More practical learning techniques, such as case studies, role-plays, and scenario-based simulations that let interns practice risk communication and counseling, should be incorporated into nursing programs to solve this (Kareem et al., 2023). Working together with obstetric teams and pharmacists could also assist nursing interns promote safe prescribing practices and get a greater understanding of the practical effects of teratogenic medications. Enhancing these educational components can boost competence and confidence in treating expectant patients. Overall, the results show that while broad awareness is encouraging, targeted educational initiatives are required to enhance knowledge of key fetal vulnerability and counseling time. Institutions can assist future nurses play a

bigger role in avoiding drug-related birth abnormalities by incorporating teratogenicity teaching into nursing training early and consistently (PAFMJ, 2023; Prenatal Care Initiation and Exposure to Teratogenic Medications, 2023).

LIMITATIONS, CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

The results of this study may not be as applicable to other contexts in Pakistan because it was restricted to three tertiary care facilities in Islamabad and used a convenience sample technique. In addition, participants may have expanded their knowledge of teratogenic medicines due to the use of self-reported surveys, which could have created response bias. Since the cross-sectional methodology records knowledge at a specific moment in time, it is unable to capture changes that occur after educational activities. Although there are limitations, the research offers important insights into nursing interns' understanding of teratogenic medications. The findings indicate a satisfactory basic understanding of teratogenicity but reveal notable deficiencies in awareness concerning the timing of pre-conception counseling and recognizing the stages when the fetus is particularly susceptible. This gap between theoretical understanding and actual practice in clinical environments underscores the need for targeted educational enhancements within nursing curricula. Structured modules on teratogenic risk assessment and safe pharmacotherapy during pregnancy should be incorporated into nursing education programs to resolve these gaps. Clinical competence can be enhanced through the implementation of interprofessional and simulation-based learning strategies that involve pharmacists and obstetricians. Additionally, hospitals should promote the involvement of residents in pharmacovigilance and antenatal counseling activities to facilitate the transfer of knowledge into practice. Further multi-center and longitudinal research is recommended to evaluate the effectiveness of such interventions and their impact on maternal-fetal safety outcomes.

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